

Scale and democracy in Turkish local governments: The case of the amalgamation initiative in Konya province

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Abstract

Efficiency and democracy are two crucial concepts during the provision of local goods and services in many developed and developing local government systems. Policy makers, quite often, appear to make delicate choices between these two rival elements. Turkey is no exception as there is always scarcity of financial sources and huge service expectations in the public, but at the same time there are growing demands for democracy. Turkey initiated a number of local reforms to reach an acceptable level of democracy and efficiency. Seeking for an optimum level has been continuing for the last 15 years. The amalgamation initiative and enlarging municipal scales have been an effective approach in these reform attempts. There is a quite contentious issue in delivering local goods and services to the public and providing democratic instances at the same time. Turkish provision of reforms has been echoed by many countries due to the tensions among economy, efficiency, and effectiveness. The study finds that prioritizing efficiency does not necessarily lead to diminishing democracy. The empirical evidence shows that these kinds of initiatives would be regarded as a journey for better delivery of services while being aware of democratic implications at local levels.

Keywords

Local government reform; efficiency; democracy; amalgamation; scale economies

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Introduction

This paper aims to examine theoretical and practical dimensions of the policies related to scale and democracy issues with special reference to local government reforms in Turkey (the 2005 Provincial Special Administration and Municipality Act and the 2012 Metropolitan Municipality Act). Despite their relatively long history in Turkey, since the second half of the 19-th century, there have been concerns that the performance of local governments fails behind the standards they are required to display. The recent reforms intend to strike a balance between scale economies and democratic priorities, by reorganizing the structure, scale, and scope of municipality and Provincial Special Administration (PSA) responsibilities. To this end, the reform both abolishes PSAs in metropolitan areas (30 provinces) and increases the minimum number of inhabitants required to form a municipality from 2000 to 5000.

This implicitly refers to an amalgamation policy. Since outside the borders of municipalities form the responsibility areas of PSAs, the reform widens the scales and sizes of PSAs (in 51 provinces) and abolishes PSAs in metropolitan areas (in 30 provinces). In other words, the responsibilities of the abolished municipalities are transferred to PSAs in the former case, whereas PSAs are abolished in favor of municipalities in the latter. There is a common belief that small scale municipalities with around 2000 inhabitants are unlikely to provide efficiency, whereas PSAs would have the necessary experience and means to produce better 'local and common services'. By the same token, metropolitan municipalities would take better care of the provision of local goods and services in metropolitan areas.

The question in this equation is about democracy: by abolishing small municipalities and small PSAs, Turkey would possibly gain economic advantages, while at the same time it would create certain concerns for democracy. As municipalities have direct contacts with the public far more than PSAs, the newly introduced laws generate some concern. This paper proposes to shed light on the question of amalgamation by evaluating the steps taken in due course by materializing primary and secondary sources at the same time. Interviews and official data are included, to illuminate social and cultural elements behind the functioning in local governments: lively debates in committees and general assembly of Konya PSA are also cited as information.²

Local Governments in Turkey

There are three levels of local governments that exist in Turkey, as specified by the Constitution: provincial special administration (PSA), municipality, and village administration. PSAs operate outside municipality areas throughout a province, by being formed automatically when a new province is created by the parliament. They have broad responsibilities, from education to health & safety, and from infrastructure to social and cultural issues, as being the main local actor in rural areas, leaving urban responsibilities to municipalities. Since a state-appointed officer, governor, filled the role of the local authority, PSAs were generally not regarded as a local government unit (Keleş, 1999: 147). The general assembly and the council of a PSA are elected, while appointed personnel, under the command of a secretary general, form the executive component of the administration. There is a recent tendency in government to devolve a vast range of power from central government ministries to these administrations in small provinces.³

² The author served as the institutional capacity adviser to Konya PSA (between 2005 and 2014) and to Konya Metropolitan Municipality (between 2012 and 2013).

³ The Strategic Plan of Konya PSA, for instance, refers to the possible transfer of responsibilities, but does not put concrete elements into practice.

The second type of local governments is represented by municipalities. They are famous for effectiveness in terms of autonomy, budget, personnel, and close relations with the public. Due to their democratic structures and integration within society, municipalities are regarded as an integral part of local democracy. Local politics are conducted by mayors and politicians in municipality councils (Kutlu, 2007: 256-7).

The third type of local governments, village administration, is not fully operational because of its scarce resources and limited responsibilities. Villages function under the umbrella of PSAs by obtaining services from them. Advancements in communication and transportation technologies render this sort of local government redundant. Some fifty years ago, villages were more autonomous, but they are no longer centers of attention neither for the public nor politicians. Formation of villages contributes to the functions of PSAs, as they are supervised through service provision arrangements.

Table 1. Local governments in Turkey and Konya

Type of local government	Before 2014		After 2014	
	Turkey	Konya	Turkey	Konya
PSA	81	1	51	0
City Municipality	95	0	51	0
District Municipality	850	31	919	31
Metropolitan Municipality	16	1	30	1
Other Municipalities (towns)	2294	174	397	0
Village Administration	34406	587	18329	0
Total	37712	794	19777	32

Data sources: Governorship of Konya Province: <http://www.konya.gov.tr> and Ministry of Environment and Urbanization: <http://www.csb.gov.tr>.

Table 2. Size of municipalities in European countries

	Average municipal size	Municipalities per 100000 people	Median municipal size (inhabitants)	Average municipal area (km ²)
Germany	7449	13,4	1710	32
UK	167898	0,6	132240	620
Turkey	57240	1,7	8595	551
Belgium	19177	5,2	12045	51
Netherlands	44816	2,2	26515	89
Hungary	3088	32,4	815	29
EU 28	5887	17,0	---	49
OECD 35	9693	10,3	---	211

Data sources: Subnational Governments in OECD Countries: Key Data 2018 Edition.

Table 1 shows that there were 81 PSAs, 3225 municipalities, 34.406 village administrations, a total of 37.712 local government units in Turkey before the introduction of the local reforms in 2014. With the 2012 Metropolitan Municipality Act becoming operational after the March 2014 local elections, the numbers of local governments dropped dramatically in PSAs, city municipalities, town municipalities and village administrations, while there was an increase in metropolitan and district municipalities. The changes indicate a great transformation towards large scale local government units.

Metropolitan areas have experienced a huge drop in numbers as Konya Province shrank from 794 to only 32. This clearly shows the intention of reformers in adopting large scale, small number of local units to deliver local goods and services.

Restructuring the scale and scope of local governments is not a problem faced by Turkey alone; it was also a problem that many European countries had to solve after the 1980s. So, the Turkish policy to take the issue on the agenda was neither baseless nor meaningless. Table 2 illustrates the size of local governments in certain OECD countries to form a basis for evaluation. The data display a great deal of uneven size structures across these countries.

Local Government Reforms

Administrative reform initiatives and trends in many countries, especially since the 1980s, have not been supported by the political and bureaucratic elite of Turkey. The problem of local governments had persisted until 2003, when the government revealed details of a reform proposal covering central and government structure, personnel, and regime. This signified an important cornerstone in the reformation of the Turkish administrative apparatus with modern management techniques. In April 2003, the Deputy PM announced the reform attempts, proposing three initiatives directed to the same end: The Basic Reform for Public Administration, The Public Personnel Regime Act, and the Local Government Reforms. The Basic Reform, was dedicated to establishing general principles to central and local administrations in order to create a framework for the other reforms. The second initiative was designed to list basic principles of personnel. The third act was designed to reorganize local governments at all levels.

The reform proposals had three main objectives. First, the government wanted to apply efficiency-oriented reforms to public administration as a landmark of single-party government after 12 years of coalitions and minority rulings. The previous period, between 1991 and 2002, witnessed the worst economic and political crisis in the Turkish history. During the period, the country experienced four major political crises (1995, 1996, 1997 and 2001), as well as three major economic crises (1994, 2000 and 2001). The reforms were intended as a response to the everlasting problems of government, given that the government has been heavily criticized during each of these crises.

Second, the government also wished to introduce something new, planned and implemented by the Justice and Development Party, which was founded in 2001 and came to power in 2002. The ruling party achieved an election victory only one year after its formation. In the 150 years of democratic history in the country, such period experienced an unprecedented development, focusing on a series of public sector reforms.

Third, the credentials of the Prime Minister have also paved the way for the introduction of reforms: Mr. Erdogan, as former mayor of Istanbul Metropolitan Municipality (between 1994 and 1998), had a negative view of bureaucracy, especially with respect to red tape and centralization of power. As an insider, his and his cabinet colleagues' views were the driving forces to democratize and increase the efficiency of local governments. Hence, nearly half of the ministers were with him in Istanbul as the bureaucrats of Municipality, i.e., Ministers of Finance, Public Works, Environment and Forestry, and Deputy PM. The cabinet was able to take and implement measures with little dispute within the party.

The official proposals for the reform were: participation, accountability, objectivity, efficiency, effectiveness, trust, and reliability (Dincer and Yilmaz, 2023). These objectives could be summarized in two words: democracy and efficiency. These points also became major components of the Amalgamation Act.

Actors and Motivation

The prospective candidacy status to the European Union facilitated reform initiatives in Turkey. The country, with a traditional bureaucratic system, has accelerated the reform of political and administrative mechanisms since the candidacy status was declared by the European Council Summit of Helsinki in December 1999. Since then, eight 'democratization packages' have been enacted in the parliament. Successive governments did not intend to hide the 'European' involvement in reforms (Kutlu, 2004). Therefore, the EU factor played a crucial role in overcoming the resistance from different segments of bureaucracy and society. Other country cases also reveal similar tendencies in reforming government structures (see, for instance, Tonnisson and Wilson, 2004, on the case of Estonia).

The EU always values local governments in facilitating democratic instances for their respective citizens, as well as obtaining efficiency and effectiveness gains at local levels. The European Charter on Local Self-Government initiated and enacted by the Council of Europe has been one of the important cornerstones of accession for the governments which have the vision to apply for EU membership (Himsworth, 2015). Therefore, one of the criteria imposed to the candidate countries in the accession negotiations, and the member states seeking the European Union financial and managerial support to their local projects from regional and structural funds is the proper application of the Charter with the intention to cultivate the principles and means imposed in due process.

National level institutions might suffer from the attitudes of the bureaucracy in Brussels with concerns relating to sovereignty and freedom, but regional and local actors usually enjoy the freedom and the protection given by the European institutions and financial supports to uphold their visions without negotiating their central governments, especially finance departments, during severe economic crises. In other words, national level actors might have differing perceptions about the EU involvements, while local actors are generally being in favor of the Union.

The Brexit experience, for example, displays a vast degree of enthusiasm as far as the local authorities are concerned. British government wants to fill in the gap left by the EU disintegration process. The British case provides information in the times when there is lack or limited EU involvement during disintegration mechanisms on their ways. Therefore, the White Paper published by the British government in February 2022 on the plans to replace the EU role by providing financial means and moral support for local governments to stand on their own feet is meaningful for obvious reasons. The need for introducing six basic types of capital as highlighted in the document would certainly be worth mentioning: physical, human, intangible, financial, social, and institutional. One can assume, with a degree of confidence, that these six dimensions form the EU policies vis-à-vis local governments. By the same token, the British government introduced a funding scheme to compensate for the missing EU funds.

The European Charter has been an integral part of local governments ever since its initiation among member and candidate countries. Local autonomy and subsidiarity principles are the two main pillars in local government provisions. The two elements shaped by local needs and desires are best applied in an institutional setting. Certainly, one of the ideas behind the two principles have been the local decision-making and implementation perspectives. The EU would like to make sure that local solid and enduring democracy could only be possible by consistent policies in the forms of local self-government and financial strengths indigenous to local government institutions. Therefore, local government reforms upholding democracy, increasing efficiency and effectiveness are always welcomed by the EU.

The ideologies of national and local politicians and the European impetus as highlighted above have played important roles in driving the reform initiative. *Adalet ve Kalkınma Partisi* (JDP) politicians have been controlling the government and the majority of local governments since November 2002, including almost every municipality and PSA in Konya. Ideologically, the party was declared to be pro-European and had been taking certain steps in due course. In line with the argument of Tonnisson and Wilson (2004: 253), JDP, representing the New Right ideology, intended to reduce the role of government in economic and political activities. The ruling politicians, including the PM, were behind the reforms. One needs also to mention the politicians working in local government councils in activating the cabinet by proposing the devolution of power to local administrations. A cursory glance at the developments reveals that people and organizations supporting the EU membership of the country also approved the reforms.

Regarding the opponents of the reforms, the list is composed of the President, the main opposition party, and the judiciary. The basic reform initiative was vetoed by the President in July 2004. The reasoning for the veto was quite contentious, as it stressed a unitary state tradition by showing resistance to subsidiary principles in local governments. The Kurdish separatist organization's demands for a 'federal state' and 'autonomous regions' for Kurds might have urged the president to veto. The fear was that devolution of power might lead eventually towards independence. This risk was widely discussed among academics and politicians: a considerable number of politicians and academics thought that this argument was baseless as democracy meant 'prosperity' for the entire nation.

The Constitutional Court also reviewed and outlawed certain parts of the reforms. Certain articles of the act were invalidated in 2004, and eventually the government had to restore and resubmit the proposal to the parliament. The act was approved by the parliament after major changes in the organization and principles. In the case of amalgamation and abolition law, the Court outlawed only minor parts of the act. However, the State Council interpreted the act differently, allowing municipalities below 2000 threshold to attend the March 2009 elections. This meant that the implementation of the act was to be postponed until the 2014 elections. This difference in interpretation led to bad feelings between the State Council and the Constitutional Court, the latter publishing, for the first time in Turkish history, a statement criticizing the State Council for being against the Constitution. The PM took a similar position, criticizing the State Council for acting as a second Constitutional Court.

Not all bureaucrats and politicians supported the reform process. An interesting example was the then governor of Konya province, who had vital power and responsibilities toward local governments, especially PSAs. He openly criticized the PSA act, by arguing that the new proposal would diminish the power of appointed governors. The reform certainly was aimed to curtail power of governors. This has been a classic example of bureaucratic resistance to administrative reform.

The main opposition party (RPP) politicians were also against the reforms. The reasoning behind their negative perception was twofold: first, reform of public administration would popularize the government; second, RPP politicians were conservative in nature. Ideological and political motivations have driven opposition politicians to oppose the reforms.

Mayors of these municipalities were also against it, as the abolition would eradicate their posts. Besides, a considerable section of the society opposed to the proposal. The idea behind the negative attitude owed very much to the individual costs-benefits of indigenous people. As examined, municipalities have large organizational structures, employing dozens of people, so the abolition meant job losses and low revenue for the local businesses.

Changes in law

The Municipality Act demands examination in evaluating amalgamation and democracy concerns. Being a main source of democracy, municipalities constituted ‘schools’ of democratic government. Other types of local authorities are also a part of democratic environment, but traditionally municipalities form the major part of local democracy in Turkey.

Table 3 shows there are 1389 municipalities in Turkey. Metropolitan municipalities are formed by metropolitan districts and therefore they are counted twice in the table: one in the metropolitan municipality the other in the metropolitan district columns. The table proves that amalgamation initiatives have been successful in creating large scale municipalities, as municipalities over 100.000 population form about 77 % of total municipal inhabitants.

Table 3. Municipalities in Turkey according to population size

Population size	Metropolitan	City	Metropolitan District	District	Town	Total	Population
< 2.000			1	39	62	102	165618
2.001 – 5.000			13	126	286	425	1285312
5.001 – 10.000			40	99	36	175	1222583
10.001 – 20.000			78	66	1	145	2072520
20.001 – 50.000		5	136	53	1	195	6144581
50.001 – 75.000		6	50	12		68	4143682
75.001 – 100.000		6	25	5		36	3188799
100.001 – 250.000		28	89	3		120	18696504
250.001 – 500.000		6	62			68	24115186
500.001 – 750.000			17			17	10302888
750.001 – 1.000.000	7		8			15	12859773
1.000.001 – 2.000.000	14					14	19127990
2.000.001 – 3.000.000	5					5	11124992
3.000.001 – 5.000.000	2					2	7423371
> 5.000.001	2					2	21158343
Total	30	51	519	403	386	1389	78362652

Data source: General Directorate for Local Authorities, *Local Governments 2019 Annual Report*.

The Oxford dictionary defines amalgamation as ‘the combining of separate organizations to form a larger organization or group, or an organization or group formed in this way’. Amalgamation technique is often deployed in local government reforms to obtain a number of objectives i.e. efficiency increase by scale economy perspectives, effectiveness increase by specifically focused and target-oriented institutions, or economy increase by limited expenditure and augmented income in organizational terms.

Many Central and Eastern European countries, especially after the collapse of the Soviet Union, and many underperforming local government systems in Europe discovered this method during the 1990s and 2000s as a solid ground to meet their efficiency and effectiveness targets (Himsworth, 2015).

It is based on the idea that specifically-designed local government structures in terms of scale and scope in functions, organizational capacity, and policies could lead to better performing agencies. This has been encouraged mainly by private sector companies, which have flexible and outcome-oriented focus as well as uniquely shaped structures. Established after careful considerations in organizational prospects, local governments were expected certainly to accelerate organizational capacities.

This motivation has been evident in local governments due to their scarcity of resources, proximity with the public, and great expectations from their fellow citizens/electorates. Administrative reform initiatives overlap the outcomes of amalgamation initiatives as has been the case of Turkey. Therefore, the amalgamation policy was thought to be the only way to foster efficiency: the issue was a long-discussed problem of reforms. Alternative policies i.e. common provision of services by the third sector or contracting-out of certain services have already been discussed. The outcome was that due to intense pressure from local political networks, lack of financial means and public choice arguments, amalgamation was chosen. The argument was that because of the public resistance to privatization and private provision of public services, amalgamation was the only available option, keeping the public services in the control of public domain. Surprisingly, there was no empirical study by policy makers to support amalgamation policy.⁴ The issue was regarded as ‘take it for granted.’

Article 8 organizes ‘Mergers and Joining,’ which are also related to scale economy goals. Villages, towns, and municipalities can merge as long as there is the free will on both sides and the distance between the places is less than five kilometers. Small administrative units are encouraged to come together to achieve efficiency (Kutlu, 2007). However, since the enactment of the law there has been no case of merger: this has not worked out.

PSAs are intended to provide public goods and services mainly to rural regions, outside municipality areas in a province. This type of local authority was introduced first in 1864 with *Vilayet Nizamnamesi* but experienced a number of changes in the law ever since. PSAs were thought to become a democratic local government; over time they have concentrated to provide services to the public. The combination of the General Assembly in 1864 was an important indication of democracy: “two Muslim and two non-Muslim would represent each district” (Kolbasi, 2020). This was happening during the Ottoman period: the Sultan of the state was the religious head. Muslims and non-Muslims were equally represented in the General Assembly, the principal decision-making body of PSAs.

Table 3 clearly shows the variety in terms of population, function, and geographical areas of municipalities, while PSAs are quite simple and unified, being subject to the same laws and regulations. Differences exist among provinces with regard to population, geographical and economical terms, yet they are uniform, say for instance, as to legal obligations.

Regarding the democracy and efficiency provisions in the act, the general principles of reform initiatives have been studied in the literature (see, for instance, Quinn, 2007). Article 11 of the act is a clear indicator of this empowerment: the general assembly of the province is given an elected president, while provincial governor was presiding previously. Article 16 scrutinizes *ad hoc* committees of general assembly, delegating certain responsibilities in respect to specific areas. Members of the assembly, elected persons, are encouraged to participate in decision making processes of PSAs. Article 22 limits the instances to dissolve the assembly. Article 31 introduces strategic planning and performance programs. Article 35 creates a new position, Secretary General, to execute decisions of the assembly. It is safe to assume that efficiency and democracy are two major goals of local government reforms.

⁴ Interview with Prof. Bilal Eryilmaz, a member of committee to propose the law (Ankara, 19.12.2018).

Amalgamation initiative

Reasons

The *Municipality Act* delegates vital responsibilities to municipalities. The act spells out the responsibilities as follows:⁵

“construction, water and irrigation, urban services like transportation, geographical and urban information systems, environment, cleaning, control, firefighting, ambulance and rescue, urban traffic, cemeteries, tree planting, park and green areas, housing, culture and arts, tourism, youth and sport, social services and aid, registration, professional and individual development, promotion of economy and commerce, education institutions” (Municipality Act, art. 14)

The list clearly imposes responsibilities on municipalities. One can correctly claim that these responsibilities place too great a burden on small municipalities. One of the criticisms of the act would be the generalist principle, as all municipalities outside metropolitan areas are deemed at the same level: a municipality with 2000 and another with one million inhabitants. For this reason, the 2014 Annual Report of the Ministry of Interior asserts the ‘scale’ problem in the following words:

“For small municipalities, there is an obvious problem of scale. With the increase of the threshold to 5000, there has been a struggle to gain efficiency in local governments. From the point of the view of scale economies, small municipalities have not been able to develop their administrative capacities; they spent majority of their incomes in running activities rather than productive areas; they could not even meet basic needs of the inhabitants. Besides, these municipalities suffer from the shortage of skilled personnel in main operational duties.”

Due to the severe economic crisis during the previous decades in Turkey, policy makers enjoyed the relatively consensual support, especially in the implementation of efficiency-based initiatives. To a greater extent this explains the warm reception by the public. Corruption allegations and lack of efficiency in central and local governments were so widespread, and therefore there were neither proper discussions in the public nor in the opposition during the introduction of amalgamation reforms.

PSAs operate outside municipal areas in certain services and inside municipal areas for others. Therefore, their service areas are quite wide-ranging both geographically and functionally. Table 1 gives the numbers of local governments in Turkey and in Konya. There were 794 local government units in Konya province in the pre-2014 period. Konya PSA’s service area was within the borders of the province, which was the largest in the country covering 41,694 km². In terms of population, Konya PSA had around 2.350 million inhabitants. Considering that it is larger than certain countries of Europe, there was a greater need to organize services of Konya in an efficient order.

The PSA Act spells out the responsibilities of the Administrations as follows:

“Health, agriculture, industry and commerce, environmental plan, infrastructure and settlements, protection of soil and prevention of erosion, social services and aid, micro credits to the needy, services for children, provision of land for schools, construction, and repairs [...] in urban areas; Infrastructure, roads, water, solid waste, environment, emergency services and aid, culture, tourism, youth and sport, support to the people living in forestry areas, tree planting, park and gardening services [...] outside municipal areas” (Provincial Special Administration Act, art. 6).

⁵ *Municipality Act*, Law No: 5393: <http://www.icisleri.gov.tr/Icisleri/Web/Gozlem2.aspx?sayfaNo=68>, Article 14

The list is a comprehensive one, touching nearly all public policy issues. The following provision in the article reads that PSAs would take discrepancies into account on social, economic and cultural matters, and therefore fulfil their responsibilities in line with their financial and economical capacities. Otherwise, such responsibilities need huge amounts of financial resources, hampering implementation processes.

One could possibly classify the services provided by PSAs as 'rough' rather than 'soft' ones. The term rough refers to limited direct contact with individuals in the service areas, whereas soft services require extensive interaction with individuals. To illustrate with examples, rough services are like roads, construction, and bringing water to municipal organizations, but not providing them directly to the public. Provisions to and relations with the public are soft types of services. Therefore, the service areas of PSAs resemble setting the scene, but playing the game is a soft service and within the realm of municipal authorities.

Regarding financial resources, PSAs have quite strong positions; the act stipulates plenty of room for maneuver: if an authority does not have enough resources, it would not be able to provide certain services. A list is made at the beginning of every financial year. Recently, PSAs have started to reorganize the formation of the lists by having a long-term strategic plan to set guidelines for the coming financial years and budgets. Certain responsibilities of PSAs have been intensified, but further financial assistance would be allocated by central government. The government proposal in the parliament to strengthen economic conditions and financial positions of PSAs created plenty of inducements (Bill for PSA and Municipality Revenues, 2007).

Concerning the proficiency of PSAs, they are usually well-equipped with experts and necessary means.⁶ Their long history presents an advantage for the performance of the administration. The principles brought by recent reforms to empower individuals and the lower echelons of civil service have the potential of establishing a fresh start for elected and appointed members of the administration. One may argue, from a different point of view, that performance comparisons of PSAs can be misleading, due mainly to the previous conditions of the administration: more data is needed. With the act, PSAs have started to take control of services they provide.

With regard to implementation of the act, Konya PSA had been trying hard to polish its image among bureaucracy and politicians as well as the public (Kutlu, 2010). To illustrate the position and direction of reform, two examples, which took place in 2009, are illuminating: the strategic plan and forming of the financial budget for 2010. As previously mentioned, strategic planning is a requirement of the PSA act. Every authority has to have a plan for at least a five-year period. This helps train local politicians and bureaucrats in planning their activities. Outside actors, stakeholders, participated in the strategic planning process in Konya, as encouraged by Article 16.

Strategic planning attempts started in April 2009 with invitations to attend the appropriate committee meetings. As stakeholders, representatives of 46 institutions, including NGOs, business associations, other local authorities, central government bureaus, universities, and professional organizations, attended the meetings. This was a success in itself, because it was one of the first attempts of a PSA to take the lead to provide a plan for the entire province. The Leader of the Assembly stated in an interview that:

⁶ Since their responsibility areas are vague to certain extent, they can allocate their financial sources with a reasonable degree of flexibility. Therefore, they have discretion to employ experts and obtain equipments.

We made a very important start there. Representatives of all institutions and individuals sit around a table and brainstormed for the future of the PSA, which has implications for the entire province. Besides, outcome was also so good, given the time constraints. We intended to create a productive and democratic local government in Konya (Ali Selvi, interview).

The architect of the plan, Mehmet Kaçmaz, also supports this argument and asserts that:

Preparation process was so painful, nobody, including myself, knew anything about the process. In addition, upon our invitation public and private organizations were not ready to come and make our policies. Therefore, they praised our efforts, confessing that they had not expected us to allow making the plan. This has been a positive message as far as democracy and efficiency are concerned (Mehmet Kaçmaz, interview).

The Secretary General and President of the Assembly spared their time, including the weekends and outside working hours. As Assembly members come from 31 districts of Konya, when they went back to their constituencies, they also praised these efforts for the sake of both democracy and efficiency.⁷ President of assembly, Mr. Ak states in an interview that

Assembly members were quite happy to see that PSA was doing something incredible, may be taking the lead from large municipalities. We were, traditionally, feeling that we provide services only to rural areas, and were not aware of plans, strategies and management. With the plan we have proven that we have understood the principles of the act, reforms (Mustafa Sabri Ak, interview)

The budget preparation story in 2013 is also interesting for democracy and efficiency discussions as a lesson for practitioners. As outlined, Article 31's requirement of performance plan was to be put into practice. The budget has to observe the guidance of strategic planning. Before the budget making process started in September, Strategic Plan committee members had come together. The Secretary General headed the committee; members included the R&D Manager, the Leader, and academic advisors. This committee decided to widen the participation, so all special committee members were involved in the process as well as including all members of the assembly. Sixteen Special Committee chairpersons met the Strategic Plan committee to explain the budget preparation procedure. They were asked to submit their proposals with feasibility reports to the committee. They were also informed to consult with their constituencies, village chairpersons, NGOs, municipalities, local councilors and so on. Mr. Izzet Tasci, head of PSA committee, called the consultations "so inspiring."

Committees were asked to prepare a priority list, so limited sources would be allocated in a most efficient manner. Lists were submitted to the Secretary General, and for every special committee a group was made, consisting of one academic advisor, one executive expert from that particular field (i.e. provincial director of education), one member of budget committee, head of budget department (bureaucrat), Secretary General and members of that particular committee. The committee came together, and after lively discussions prepared its final document.

During the preparation process, interesting disputes also occurred. At the Youth and Sport Committee meeting, for instance, after harsh criticism from the head of the committee to the head of the budget department, there was even a strong dispute between the parts.⁸ The meetings turned out

⁷ As an involved actor, the author also felt that assembly members and bureaucrats noticed once again that the conditions of the forthcoming period would be different from those of the previous.

⁸ The head of the budget, Mrs. G. Nese Uyar was arguing that she knows the law and the committee did not have any authority in budget preparation. Head of the committee, on the other hand, was arguing that he was an elected person and supposed to make final decisions.

to be a platform for power disputes between elected politicians and appointed personnel. This was logical, because reform discussions in the country for the last 15 years have been reiterating the importance of democracy and efficiency, and this notion was inspired by public choice arguments, empowering elected persons. In some cases, however, elected politicians were debating who would make final decisions in certain matters. The President and the Leader of the Majority were trying to compromise individuals working in the PSA. The Leader, Mr. Selvi, says in an interview that:

“we have practiced real democracy over there. On the one hand, conditions of the services have to be respected, on the other; elected people have to take the control. This is our task: to balance democracy and efficiency.”

The President also worked very hard to ease the tension by saying that:

“Important thing is to please the public. That is why we are here. Besides, we have to make concessions to please the elected and non-elected ones. We represent 2.3 million people here. We have vital responsibilities. We have to provide water; we have to build schools and so on. Democracy is important, but efficiency is also important.”

Looking at the outcome, elected members enjoyed their rights and responsibilities by exercising them in a vital matter, budget allocations. Compared to their previous position, which allowed only certain matters and a limited period to make decisions, the new act empowered committee members for wider periods and issues. This was more democratic and might have had better opportunities for the sake of efficiency.

Goals

Plurality and variety are the concepts for democratic regimes in promoting discussions on democracy and efficiency as they have obvious roots stemming from very basic principles of democracy and managerial techniques. By the same token, amalgamation initiative in Turkey might create better opportunities for PSAs. The interim period, between 2005 and 2014, was thought to be vital to adopt to the new era both emotionally and organizationally⁹.

The validity of the arguments for and against small municipalities should be examined from the points of the view of democracy and efficiency. The basic argument of scale economies appears to be strong, because small municipalities do not have real prospects for optimum use of financial and administrative apparatus. Lack of skilled personnel and other means might hamper their operations. There is little chance of optimum use due mainly to the scarcity of resources on the one hand, and too many responsibilities and deprivation in small local units on the other. As the budget conditions of Bolat and Demirci municipalities clearly show, the increase of the threshold is not enough; a few hundred above or below 2000 does not make any difference regarding efficiency.

The mayor of a municipality which has less than 2000 population provided some solutions:

“Article 13 of the municipality act, the Membership Right of a Community, gives us some flexibility to generate our financial resources. Members of municipal communities could be inspired to take active parts in municipal affairs; they might become sponsors of our projects. At the moment, our budget is nothing. It is not enough to fulfil all our responsibilities. We have to try to obtain and make money for our services. By erasing a very basic level of local authority,

⁹ It was the observation of the author that when he contacted the mayors, they seemed to be excited with an expectation of raising their voices to be able to keep the municipalities. They were stressing on the importance of the municipalities to foster democracy and economy. One of the arguments was the lack of debts in their respective authorities. They claimed that this is a sort of proof of success.

municipality, the government is not doing the right thing. This must have been asked by the EU, which does not know our conditions” (Anonymous, interview).

This argument might seem to be solid on the claim of democracy, but certain other dimensions also require examination. Hence, abolished municipalities would become village administrations, which would have village headpersons with little personnel and running costs. In addition, there are more flexible arrangements in the Village Act than Article 13, which is already explained. The act allows headpersons to impose financial responsibilities on inhabitants of villages. In other words, headpersons may generate the same money from the same sources. Since they have simple structures and very limited budgets, they are more likely to obtain goods and services for their communities as villages are more sympathetic to central government bureaucrats than municipalities.

From a different angle, a resident of a municipality brings a different explanation to the issue and claims that:

“if losing municipality would bring more service to me, I would prefer services. If the money spent in running costs would be allocated to create services, I would prefer services. For me, better living conditions are more important than better organizational structures” (Ahmet Canli, interview)

His arguments are quite realistic from the efficiency point of view.

In addition, village administrations are also named as local government units by the Constitution. Article 127 details the names and operation principles of local governments. Therefore, transforming municipalities into village administrations would not be deemed as lifting democracy and local governments; a different democratic logic works in villages: less bureaucracy, less government, and less state. This might even be proposed as a better type of democracy. Since direct democracy is regarded as the best alternative, democracy is quite direct in villages. Every important decision is taken by popular vote (referendum) in villages. In reality, however, direct democracy does not work in the way described, as there is little incentive to motivate people to participate. Besides, there is a growing need to seek better ways of creating democratic instances to include people of small-scale municipalities. They would be given better chances and more opportunities to express themselves. The recent exercise of arranging the meetings of Provincial Chamber in Districts might help enhance democracy in small local governments. Yet, other ways of participation and creating democratic instances are open for discussion. As the Secretary General states, “Konya PSA was ready to apply democratic techniques” (Mehmet Kacmaz, interview).

Policy initiatives and practices

For the new period, PSAs had been specially designed to implement policies to rural areas, (villages). This arrangement brought new financial and administrative capacities to them. Previously, villages were also provided services at discretion of PSA councils, but the new provision makes sure that all villages are treated in the same manner. The initiative is called KÖY-DES (Village-Support) project.

The project started to be implemented by the decision of Ministry of Interior. The initiative focuses mainly on four services for villages: roads, drinking water, soil and small water reservoirs and sewer systems. Having specified the type of services to be provided regarding quality and quantity, the Ministry intends to fill the gap left by municipalities. It was thought that only PSAs could perform the job. For Konya PSA, the amount of money allocated is as follows: 2.5m in 2010, 34m in 2011, and 29.7m TL in 2012. The KÖY-DES project budget is an extra source, and therefore not included in PSA budget. Considering that the budget of the Administration was 180m TL in 2012, this amount was fascinating, constituting 37 % of the PSA budget.

Two municipality budgets are taken for comparison to get a better insight into the issue. The municipalities, Bolat and Demirci, are randomly selected for review. They are within Konya province and one of them had population less than 2000, and the other over. According to a recent population census Bolat had 1793 inhabitants, while Demirci had 2213. It is surprising to note that the number of inhabitants in 2000 were 4030 in Bolat and 2696 in Demirci. One of the reasons for the decrease in numbers has been the economic conditions of municipalities. Due to high unemployment rates, these administrative units have been losing populations.¹⁰ Another reason was the 'fake' counting, cheatings. During the counting seasons, people used to register themselves in their small hometowns, mainly municipalities.¹¹ Better methods in census help establish correct numbers and data.

Table 4. Municipality budgets

Type of allocation	Bolat		Demirci	
	Amount	% of total	Amount	% of total
Personnel costs	497000	36,76%	420000	51,52%
Other running costs	460000	34,02%	247084	30,32%
Investments cost	395000	29,22%	148000	18,16%
Total	1352000	100,00%	815084	100,00%

Data sources: Bolat Municipality mayor and Demirci Munic.

Table 4 displays details of budgets in general terms to illustrate the financial situations of municipalities. The figures in the table clearly point out that small municipalities spend most of their budget allocations to running costs, rather than investment and provision of goods and services to respective local units. Certainly, the intention of reformers was to spare money to productive areas. Though one cannot claim that investment is good for productivity and running costs are not, yet there is a general feeling that without investing, organizations could not become productive. The statement by the Mayor of Akören District, with 10114 inhabitants, is illuminating:

“Financially we are really in a difficult position. Majority of the money allocated from the central government goes to personnel expenses. I try very hard to spare some money to infrastructure, social projects, and cultural aspects. I have to have a list of priorities. Without providing water, for instance, I cannot spend in culture. So, I am trying to reduce the burden of personnel on my budget” (Tahir Dinc, Interview).

Personnel costs in Bolat are more than a third of the total budget. In addition, running costs such as heating, lighting, and cleaning the service buildings are about one third, namely 34.02 %. As to investment costs, the municipality can only allocate 29.22%. Clearly, the figures are not acceptable, because these places are less developed in the terms of GDP and therefore need productive investments (European Commission, 2007). The Demirci municipality is no better than Bolat, as personnel costs here are around 51.52%: over the half of budget goes to personnel costs. Other running costs are again quite high in Demirci, representing 30.32%. Investment costs are only 18.16%, which confirms explicitly that Demirci cannot even allocate money to very basic service provisions.

¹⁰ The rate of urbanization dropped from 36% to 27% between 2003 and 2007.

¹¹ Since the income of municipalities depends solely on the number of inhabitants; municipalities invited their fellow friends to their hometowns. After counting, people would go their homes. The new population act of 2006 does not rely on counting days, and introduced IT and keep databases. Once persons move from a place to another their records also move that particular place.

Regardless of whether the municipalities would lose their positions, small municipalities are not able to provide the services they are supposed to. Available financial resources and responsibilities listed in the Municipality Act do not seem to be in line. Leaving aside the cultural and social responsibilities of municipalities, even very essential ones are in danger of desertion.

The mayor of Bolat, Mr. Ibrahim Meki, claimed in an interview that their local authority was successful, and therefore they should be able to preserve it after 2014. A survey conducted by a specialist local government website reveals successful results for the mayor: around 52% of respondents think that the mayor was quite successful, 3% said successful, 4% said no idea, and 41% of respondents thought that he was not successful. Therefore, given the conditions, Mr. Mayor appeared to be successful, but the municipal system was not.

Inhabitants of municipalities, however, are not ready to lose their authorities for practical and emotional reasons. Living in a municipality is more prestigious than a village. People feel degraded if they lose their municipality. It can be attributed to the urbanization process, as it brings a new culture and new attitudes. Inhabitants feel that their local government forms a part of their identity. Besides, people in municipalities are provided with certain municipal services by an authority nearby. This is a source of motivation for inhabitants of municipalities as well. Villages, located one level below municipalities, do not provide the services supplied by municipalities. To this end one interviewee states that:

“having a municipality is important for us. We do not want to lose it. It facilitates our lives. We do not have to go to district or to the city for public services. The services are brought to us, rather than we go there” (Anonymous, Interview).

The person seems to be conscious about the importance of having a municipality.

Conclusions

Local government reforms in Turkey have been concerned about efficiency and democracy especially for the last 15 years. On the one hand, local authorities are designed to implement democracy by empowering the public and individuals in the provision of local goods and services; on the other, economical concerns drive the changes to obtain optimum use of scarce resources.

Provisions of the Municipality Act in abolishing small municipalities seems to be a type of amalgamation. By widening its responsibility areas, the Act appears to trust the PSAs against harsh local economic conditions. Histories and current administrative and operational capacities of these administrations pose a considerable amount of evidence for future success. Besides, evidence obtained during the examination proves that small-scale municipalities fall behind the expectations of politicians as well as inhabitants. Interestingly, though, some inhabitants still want to keep their municipalities. They oppose to the amalgamation, as they feel that local authorities are important to their identities. The reform would go beyond the 2000 person requirement and increase the threshold to 5000 person to catch scale economies in the future. The reactions of the actors show that efficiency is more important than democracy in amalgamation initiatives. Bearing in mind that resident numbers in the 2000 census were higher in many municipalities, this minimum number would probably become meaningless in a few years. Ultimately, even the 5000 person requirement could not provide efficiency. One can rightly ask a question: What is the correct number? This study found that there is no ‘correct’ number. Conditions of the country determine the correct level: ‘the jury is still out’.

There is a strong need to find other ways of including individuals in the activities of PSAs as they have been acting to promote participation at all levels and instances. The reforms seem to provide necessary mechanisms for the implementation of democratic principles among assembly members.

Konya PSA acted enthusiastically to foster democracy by taking power from appointed officers and handing it to elected politicians. The quotes given from the Konya case highlight the feasibility and applicability of demolishing municipalities and establishing scale economies.

In addition, the abolition of PSAs in metropolitan areas was designed to meet the needs for efficiency concerns, just like the change of minimum number of 5000 people in forming municipalities in a local unit. Therefore, Turkey adopted the policy of larger local government units to facilitate the 'value for money' approach; every effort has been made in establishing scale economies, but the anxieties from the point of the view of democracy would not be eradicated completely.

In conclusion, the reforms to increase efficiency of local authorities have got backing both from organizational and functional points of view. Democracy is meaningful only with efficiency. This study finds that the reforms do not pose any threat to democracy in the era of limited resources and unlimited expectations from the public. A municipality would be converted to a village administration or to a metropolitan municipality, from one form of local government to another. Consequently, democracy in local governments is being balanced with certain organizational changes, but local governments would have to search other ways and means of implementing democracy too.

List of people interviewed

The following people have been interviewed for this paper: Mr. Mustafa Sabri Ak (President of General Assembly of Konya PSA), Mr. Ahmet Canli, Mr. Tahir Dinc (Mayor of Akoren District), Prof. Dr. Bilal Eryilmaz (Member of the committee to propose the law), Mr. Mehmet Kacmaz (Secretary General of Konya PSA), Mr. İbrahim Meki (Mayor of Bolat), Mr. Ali Selvi (Leader of Konya PSA), Mr. Mehmet Sogut (R&D Manager of Konya PSA). Two other interviews have been conducted but the interviewees required to not have their names published.

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